

PROCESSING AND CHARACTERIZATION OF FLY ASH PARTICLE REINFORCED A356 AL COMPOSITES

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ABSTRACT: In the present study Aluminium alloy (A356) metal matrix composites (Al-MMCs) containing 12 vol. % of fly ash particles have been fabricated using stir-cast technique. Two types of fly ash particles used are wide size range (0.5 to 400 μ m) and narrow size range (53 to 106 μ m) particles. The cast and extruded composites and unreinforced materials were characterized by optical microscopy (OM), and scanning electron microscopy (SEM). Mechanical properties studied include hardness, elastic modulus, tensile and compressive properties and damping behaviour. Narrow size range particle reinforced composites shows better property compared to composites containing particle of wide range size particles.

KEYWORDS: Al-MMCs, fly ash, stir-cast technique and damping capacity.

INTRODUCTION

There is an increasing interest in composites containing low density and low cost reinforcements. Among the various discontinuous dispersoids used, fly ash is one of the most inexpensive and low-density reinforcement available in large quantities as solid waste by-product during combustion of coal in thermal power plants. Hence, composites with fly ash as reinforcement are likely to overcome the cost barrier for wider use in automotive and small engine applications. Thus the incorporation of waste fly ash particles in aluminium alloy will promote yet another use of this low-cost waste by product and, at the same time, has the potential for conserving energy-intensive aluminium and thereby, reducing the cost of aluminium products [1-3]. After recognizing the immense potential of Al-fly ash composites, experiments were done to fabricate A356 Al-fly ash composites and characterize these composites for their microstructure, mechanical properties and damping behaviour.

MATERIALS AND EXPERIMENTAL PROCEDURE

The materials used in this study were A356 Al – 12 volume % fly ash particles composites containing two size ranges of fly ash particles. One is narrow size range (53 to 106 μ m) and another wide size range (0.5 to 400 μ m) fly ash particle. Composites were fabricated using stir-cast technique. The chemical composition of matrix alloy and fly ash particles are shown in Table 1 and 2. Fly ash from Raichur thermal power plant (India) was used in this study its characteristics are shown in Table 3 and their SEM micrographs are shown in Fig. 1.

Table 1: Chemical composition of Al-Si alloy (A356) in weight percent

Si	Mg	Fe	Cu	Mn	Cr	Ti	Al
7.083	0.409	0.097	0.059	0.003	0.012	0.132	balance

Table 2: Chemical composition of fly ash in weight percent

SiO ₂	Al ₂ O ₃	Fe ₂ O ₃	CaO	MgO	TiO ₂
64.80	24.01	5.23	2.76	0.90	0.50

Table 3: Characterization of Raichur fly ash

Fly ash	Particle size, D ₅₀ (μm)	Density (g/cc)	Loss on Ignition
As Received	58.77	2.10	1.33
Sieved	76.43	2.09	0.87

The A356 Al-fly ash composites were fabricated by stir casting technique. The experimental set-up used in this study is shown schematically in Fig. 2. In the present work, A356 Al-fly ash [particle of as received (D₅₀ ~ 60 μm) and sieved (D₅₀ ~ 76 μm)] composites were fabricated using stir casting technique. Fly ash particles were preheated to 800°C for 2 hour and then dispersed into the vortex (created by mechanical stirring) of the A356 Al alloy melt held at 770°C and subsequently cast into 60 mm diameter cast iron moulds. A356 Al - 12 volume % as-received fly ash composite [C12(AR)] and A356 Al - 12 volume % sieved fly ash composite [C12(S)] were prepared. The unreinforced alloy was also processed under identical conditions for the purpose of comparison. The cast ingots machined to a size of 55mm diameter were homogenized at 530°C for 2hr and extruded at an extrusion ratio of 21:1.

In the present work a GABO EPLEXOR[®] dynamic mechanical thermal analyzer (DMTA) was used to measure the damping capacity [4]. The damping specimens are rectangular bars with the dimension of 2 X 10 X 50 mm. The samples are made from the as extruded rods. Symmetric three point bending technique was used to measure the dynamic modulus and damping capacity. The test was done under a dynamic load of 10 N, static load of 20 N and the frequency of 10Hz.

Fig. 1: SEM micrograph of fly ash particles (a) precipitator and (b) cenosphere

Fig. 2: Schematic diagram of the stir casting set up used in fabrication of A356 Al-fly ash composite

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Fly ash particles are spherical in shape. Most of the fly ash consists of solid, partially solid, or hollow spherical particles. The fly ash particles are generally in the form of solid spheres known as precipitator fly ash or in the form of hollow spheres termed as cenosphere fly ash. The fly ash used in this study had a wide particle size distribution. The particle size of the fly ash, in the as-received condition, lies in the range from 0.5 to 400 μm . Hence, as received particles were sieved and those particles, which pass through 140 mesh and retained on 270 mesh were chosen. Particle size analysis was done using a computerized particle size analyzer, Malvern[®] make laser light particle size analyzer (Mastersizer). 50% (D_{50}) of the as received particles were less than 59 μm with an average particle size of 89 μm . In the case of sieved particles (-140 # +270#), 50% of the particles were less than 76 μm had an average size of 81 μm .

Microstructures of as cast composites reveal relatively uniform distribution of fly ash particles in the matrix (Fig. 3). However, at some locations clusters of smaller fly ash particles and pores were observed. Hot extrusion leads to substantial improvement in the integrity of microstructure of composites (Fig. 4). Particles and eutectic silicon were aligned in the extrusion direction (Fig. 4b). The aluminium from the matrix would react with SiO_2 and Fe_2O_3 and magnesium reacts with SiO_2 and Al_2O_3 constituents of the fly ash [2, 5]. The average density of C12(AR) composite is 2.60 gm/cc and the average density of C12(S) composite is 2.59 gm/cc as compared to a density of 2.68 gm/cc for the unreinforced alloy. The silicon and fly ash particles are aligned along the extrusion direction in the composites. There is no significant agglomeration/segregation of fly ash particle.

Hardness

The macrohardness and microhardness of the alloy and composites were shown in Fig. 5. Brinell macrohardness measurements were made in order to assess the bulk hardness of

(a)

(b)

Fig. 3: OM microstructure of as cast (a) C12 (S) composite and (b) C12 (AR) composite

(a)

(b)

Fig. 4: Optical micrographs of C12(S) composite (a) transverse and (b) longitudinal section

the materials. The Vickers microhardness measurements were made on the aluminium matrix, far away from fly ash particles to provide insight on the effect of fly ash on the matrix hardness. The results show considerable increase in both the bulk hardness and micro hardness due to the additions of fly ash and this could be attributed to the hard aluminosilicate particles.

Tensile properties

In the extruded condition, composites [C12 (AR) and C12 (S)] show higher 0.2 % proof stress than the unreinforced alloy. It indicates that the fly ash additions improve the yield strength considerably. Composites exhibit lower UTS compared to that of unreinforced alloy. It is due to the presence of pores, clustering of particles and the formation of second phase particles in the matrix and at particle / matrix interfaces. C12(S) composite shows higher 0.2% proof stress and ultimate tensile strength compared to C12(AR) composite in the as extruded condition. The drastic reduction in the percent elongation of 12-volume % fly ash

reinforced composites could be attributed to the presence of pores, particle clusters and other defects.

Fig. 5: Hardness of alloy and its composites in the extruded condition

The fracture surface of tensile specimens of composites shows mixed mode (ductile and brittle) fracture [Fig. 6]. Dimples come mainly due to the fracture of α -aluminium, whereas interface as well as eutectic Si regions exhibit brittle fracture. Hollow (Cenosphere) fly ash particles show fracturing and also good interfacial bonding [Fig. 6b], whereas fly ash particles, which have been partially bonded with the matrix show an interfacial gap resulting in debonding from the matrix [Fig. 6c]. At macro level, the fracture surfaces of the composites appeared to be flat, indicating lower ductility of composites. The brittle nature of the fracture surfaces is consistent with low elongation values obtained during the tensile test. On the microscopic level, it is worth noting that the fly ash particles exhibit characteristic brittle fracture, surrounded by the dimples in the adjoining matrix, i.e. mixed mode of fracture. Two concurrent damage mechanisms such as matrix voiding and particle cracking have been observed. Presence of cracked particle in composites also confirms excellent bonding between the particle and the matrix.

(a)

(b)

(c)

Fig. 6: SEM micrographs showing the fractured surfaces of composite

Compressive properties

Table 4. compares the compressive and tensile yield stress of the unreinforced alloy and their composites. Under compressive loading condition, 0.2% proof stress of as-extruded composites are higher than the unreinforced alloy. 0.2% compressive proof stress also follows the same trend as 0.2% tensile proof stress. However, 0.2% compressive proof stress of unreinforced alloy and their composites were higher than the 0.2% tensile proof stress. Compressive strength of the composite is lower than the unreinforced alloy due to porosity and particle clustering.

Table 4: Mechanical properties of alloy and its composites

Material	Tensile properties			Compressive properties	
	0.2% Proof Stress (MPa)	UTS (MPa)	% Elongation	0.2% Proof Stress (MPa)	Compressive Strength (MPa)
A356 Al	83.19	165	24	90.39	458.37
C12(S)	109.20	145	13	107.69	426.54
C12 (AR)	91.03	142	10	106.47	416.99

Damping capacity

The damping capacity ($\tan \phi$) and dynamic modulus (E) data for unreinforced alloy and their composites at room temperature are shown in Table 5. The test was done at 10Hz frequency. The modulus and the damping capacity are higher in fly ash reinforced composites as compared to unreinforced alloy. The increment in the damping capacity of 12-volume % fly ash reinforced composites were 1.5 times the unreinforced alloy.

Both damping capacity and dynamic modulus versus temperature at a frequency of 10 Hz are shown in Fig. 7. The plots are scaled identically along the damping capacity axis in order to allow direct comparison. Several interesting trends may be noted from Fig. 7, which are found to be characteristic of all extruded unreinforced alloy and composites. Firstly, the elastic modulus decreases with increasing temperature. Secondly, the damping capacity

increases with increase in temperature. Lastly, the damping capacity is found to rapidly increase with increasing temperature above 200°C. At least three samples for each of the materials were tested on the DMTA to verify repeatability. Zhang *et al.* [6] have also shown an increase in damping capacity with increasing temperature in the case of SiC, Al₂O₃ and graphite particle-dispersed aluminium matrix composites.

From Fig. 7. it is clear that the damping capacity of 12-volume % fly ash reinforced composites are much higher than the unreinforced alloy in the temperature range measured. The improved damping capacity of the composites could be attributed to the presence of fly ash particulate reinforcement and the concomitant modification in the microstructure of the aluminium alloy matrix. The modified microstructural characteristics include: finer grain size, thermal mismatch induced dislocations and particle / matrix interfaces. In MMCs, point defect damping is relatively small compared to other sources of defects damping. The dislocations contribute to damping by the motion of vibrating dislocation lines, viscous sliding of grain boundaries and mobility of interfaces. The damping capacity in the MMCs is directly related to each of the aforementioned damping mechanisms in ceramic reinforcement and metal matrix [7].

Table 5: Damping capacity and modulus values of A356 Al and its composites at 10 Hz

Material	Reinforcement		At RT (26 ± 1) °C	
	Vol. %	Particle Size, D ₅₀ (µm)	tan φ	E (GPa)
A356 Al	-	-	0.028	71
C12(S)	12	76	0.040	76
C12(AR)	12	59	0.041	74

Fig. 7: Effect of temperature on modulus and damping capacity of A356 Al and its composites

CONCLUSIONS

1. The average density of C12(AR) composite samples is of the order of 2.60 gm/cc. Whereas, the average density of C12(S) composite was of the order of 2.59 gm/cc as compared to a density of 2.68 gm/cc for the matrix alloy.
2. Bulk hardness (macro) and matrix microhardness of A356 Al-fly ash composites are higher compared to those of the unreinforced alloy.
3. In the as extruded condition, 0.2 % proof stress of A356 al-fly ash composites is higher compared to that of unreinforced alloy.
4. Additions of fly ash lead to reduction in % elongation of composites. Decrease in UTS and % elongation could be attributed to the presence of porosity, particle clustering, defects and reaction products in the matrix and at particle/matrix interfaces.
5. 0.2 % compressive proof stress values are higher than the 0.2 % tensile proof stress in both unreinforced alloy and their composites.
6. Fracture surface of composites show mixed mode (ductile and brittle) fracture. Matrix voiding and particle fracture are the fracture mechanisms in composites. Presence of defects and the porosity are the additional factors responsible for the failure of composites. Both particle fracture and interfacial debonding are observed.
7. A356 Al-fly ash MMCs exhibit superior damping characteristics compared to unreinforced alloy both at ambient temperatures and at elevated temperatures.
8. The C12(AR) composite exhibits best damping capacity and C12(S) composite shows highest modulus at room temperature.
9. Narrow size range particle reinforced composites shows better properties compared to composites with the wider size range particle.

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